

The Status of Bismaleimides For Composites

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Summary

A review of bismaleimides covering the period from 1948 to the present was made. The chemistry of bismaleimides, leading to bismaleimide homopolymers, and copolymers is discussed. Some properties of State-of-the art and more advanced poly (bismaleimides) in resin form and in composites are presented. The advantages and disadvantages of bismaleimides are also discussed.

Introduction

This paper reviews bismaleimides covering the period 1948 to the present. The emphasis on this review is the chemistry and properties of bismaleimides for application to advanced fiber reinforced composites.

Discussion

Bismaleimides (BMI's) were first synthesized by Searle in 1948 (1), and by several investigators since then (2) 3 (4) (Fig 1).

Figure 1. Synthesis of Bismaleimides

Bismaleimides can be converted to homopolymers, copolymers, terpolymers, and can be used as cross-linking agents. The first successful homopolymerization of bismaleimides into thermoset polymers was accomplished by Grundschober and Sambeth (5) in 1968 (Fig.2).

(Ref. 5) Grundschober & Sambeth (1968)

Figure 2. Discovery of Cross-Linked Poly(Bismaleimides)

Since 1968, several publications on homopolymerization of bismaleimides have appeared in the literature (6-17) (Fig. 3).

(Ref. 6-17)

Figure 3. Bismaleimide Homopolymers

Sheremeteva (18), Grundschober (19) and other investigators (2,3) demonstrated the versatility of the maleimide double bond by copolymerization with aromatic diamines via a Michael addition reaction to form thermoset polymers with high glass transition temperatures, (T_g 's) (Fig 4).

Figure 4. Discovery of Michael Addition Polymers of Bismaleimides

The reaction of bismaleimides with olefins also yields cross-linked polymers with high glass transition temperatures ($\sim 300^\circ\text{C}$) (20-32). (Figure 5).

Ar = Aromatic
 = Aliphatic
 = Polyoxyethylene
 = Alkenyl

(Ref. 20-32)

Figure 5. Bismaleimide — Olefin Copolymers

The discovery of bismaleimides as cross-linking agents was reported by Kovacic and Hein (33) in 1959 (Fig. 6)

Figure 6. Early Studies with Bismaleimides

A special case of bismaleimide as a cross-linking agent was discovered by Liebowitz (34). This is uniquely demonstrated by the nadic-end capped PMR type (35) prepolymer imide, which undergoes a retrograde Diels-Alder (RDA) reaction, yielding bismaleimide and cyclopentadiene, followed by a recombination of these components into a highly cross-linked polyimide structure (Fig. 7).

(Ref. 34) Liebowitz (1970)

Figure 7. Special Case of Bismaleimide

The early applications of homopolymers and copolymers of bismaleimides have been as matrices for glass fiber laminates used as circuit boards for the electronics industry. More recently, the need to extend the use temperature of advanced fiber reinforced composites from 250°F hot-wet to 350-400°F hot-wet, has generated considerable interest in bismaleimides.

Commercial bismaleimides are marketed essentially in three distinct forms:

- (1) Bismaleimides or mixture of bismaleimides (Fig. 8).
- (2) Bismaleimide and Bismaleimide-aromatic amine oligomer mixtures (Fig. 8, 9).
- (3) Bismaleimide-olefins monomer mixtures and/or oligomers (Fig. 10).

Kerimid 601

Kerimid FE 70003

Completely aromatic

Rhone-Poulenc

Kerimid 353

Figure 8. Commercial Bismaleimides

Figure 9. Bismaleimide (H795) (Technochemie GmbH — West Germany)

4,4'-Bismaleimidodiphenylmethane

Component A:

0,0'-Diallyl Bisphenol A

Component B:

(Ref. 31)

Figure 10. BMI — Olefin Resins

More recent bismaleimides include the product derived from the copolymerization of a bismaleimide with p-aminobenzoic acid hydrazide (36) (Fig. 9) and crosslinked product from copolymerization of bismaleimide with a diolefin (31) (Fig. 10).

The glass transition temperatures (T_g 's) of several BMI materials are shown in Table 1. T_g 's vary from 200 to 400°C depending on the BMI structure and added components in the resin composition. The reactivity of aromatic and aliphatic bismaleimides, as well as aliphatic bis(citracon-itaconimides) are compared (36, 37) (Table 2).

TABLE 1
GLASS TRANSITION TEMPERATURES OF
POLY(BISMALEIMIDES)

System	T_g , °C	System	T_g , °C
	188	Kerimid 353	285
		Kerimid 601	290
		Kerimid FE70003	400
	60	Avco BMI	301
		Mitsubishi BT	310
		Hexcel F178	260
	~ 300	Ferro 2272	229
		Ciba-Geigy XU-292	273
		Narmco 5245C	200

TABLE 2
REACTIVITY OF BISMALEIMIDES

	Reaction rate constant, k , sec^{-1} at °C				
	n	235	240		
	6	0.0022			
	12		0.0028		
	6	132	136	138	150
	8		0.018		
	10			0.023	
	12	0.012			0.020
		235			
		0.0029			

(Ref. 35, 37)

It can be seen that aromatic and aliphatic bismaleimides have essentially equivalent reaction rate constants. It is also apparent that to increase the reactivity and/or the cure rate in a bismaleimide mixture, the addition of bis(citracon-itaconimides) is required. Bis(citraconimides) would also have the same effect (38). A list of commercially available BMI's and BMI prepregs are listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3

COMMERCIAL BMI PREPREGS

- Ferro CPI-2272, CPI-2278
- Narmco 5245 C, 5250
- Ciba Geigy R6451
- Am. Cyanamide Cycom 3100
- Hexcel F178, 1516
- Hysol EA9102, EA9655
- Technochemie H795
- U.S. Polymeric V378A, XV388, XV398
- Fiber Resin Corp BMI-9200
- AVCO BMI 130 and 151

Some properties of state-of-the art and novel commercial BMI resins are listed in Tables 4 and 5 and some properties of state-of-the art and novel BMI composite systems are listed in Tables 6, 7 and 8. The general properties of bismaleimide cross-linked polymers are listed in Table 9.

TABLE 4
STATE-OF-THE-ART BMI'S
Resin properties

	Hexcel F178	Narmco 5245C	U.S. Polymeric V378A	Mitsubishi BT 2600	Rhone- Porilene 601
Tg°C - dry	260	220		290	290
wet	140 ¹	-			
Tensile strength, ksi					
RT - dry	8.14	12.0	11.3	5.95	15.3 (flex) 11.9 - aged 1650 hrs, 250°C
wet	-	-	-	-	
250°C - dry			6.4		
Tensile-strain- to-failure, %					
RT - dry	1.3	2.9	-	-	-
Fracture toughness G _{ic} J/m ²	29.4	79	-	-	-
Moisture absorption, wt%	3.7	-	-	0.11	4.5

1. Moisture condition, not started

TABLE 5

NOVEL BMI'S
Resin properties

	Cycrom 3100	Hysol EA9102	Hysol EA9655	Techno- Chemie H795	Ciba-Geigy XU-295	Kerimide FE70003
Tg°C - dry	300	298	253	290	310	400
wet	-	210	118	-	297 ³	-
Tensile strength, ksi						
RT - dry		8.5	7.5	13.05	11.9	
wet		-	5.7 ¹		12.8 ³	
177°C - dry		6.3	3.9		-	
wet		-			6.9 ³ (150°C)	
Tensile-strain- to-failure, %						
RT - dry	2.1	2.2	1.6	2.2	2.3	
177°C - dry	2.2	3.3	2.2	-	-	
wet	3.0 ¹	-	-	-	3.4 (150°C)	
250°C - dry		-	-	2.0	-	
Fracture toughness G _{ic} J/m ²	-	-	-	-	210	-
Moisture absorption, wt%	-	-	-	4.85	1.4	1.7

1. Not stated

2. 106°F, water boil

3. 100°F, 100% RH, 2 weeks

TABLE 6

STATE-OF-THE-ART BMI's

Composite properties

	Narmco 5245C/ IM6	Hexcel F178/ T-300	Ferro CPI2272/ T-300	U.S. Polymeric V378A/ T-300	Avco 130/ T-300
Short beam shear strength, ksi					
RT - dry	16.0	15.2	14.0	18.6	19.5
wet	-	-	12.0 ¹		
135° - dry	13.5	-	-		
177° - dry	-	-	9.6	10.9	11.6
wet	-	-	9.0 ¹	7.4 ²	
232° - dry	-	10.6	-	9.2	11.0

1. 24 hrs, water boil

2. 82°C, 8 weeks, 98% RH

TABLE 7

NOVEL BMI SYSTEMS

	Composite properties			
	Ciba Geigy R6451/ T-300	Ferro CPI2278/ T-300	Narmco 5250/ celion 6000	Hexcel 1516 T-500
Short beam shear strength, ksi				
RT - dry	16.3	15.2	20.0	20.5
wet	14.0 ¹	13.5 ²	-	-
177°C - dry	11.6		12.5	15.0
wet	7.8 ¹		-	10.3 ³
232°C - dry	9.6	11.8 ²	-	11.3
wet	6.3 ¹	9.7	-	7.2 ³
250°C - dry	-		-	
177°C - dry	7.4		-	
aged 1000 hrs, 232°C				

1. 95% RH, 15 days 150°F

2. 48 hrs water boil

3. 24 hrs water boil

TABLE 8

NOVEL BMI SYSTEMS

Short beam shear strength, ksi	Composite properties			
	Hysol EA9102/ E-XAS	Am Cyan. Cycom 3100/ Celion 6000	Ciba Geigy XU 292/ AS-4	Techno- Chemie H795/ Celion 6000
RT - dry	18.0	20.5	17.8	13.5
wet	-	-	-	11.9
177°C - dry	13.0	11.8	11.9	10.7 (150°C)
wet	9.0 ¹	7.8 ²	7.7	7.5 ³ (150°C)
232°C - dry	-	-	11.4	-
wet	-	-	-	-
250°C - dry	-	-	-	5.5
177°C - dry	-	-	8.1	7.4 (250°C)
aged 1000 hrs, 232°C	-	-	-	-

1. 48 hrs water boil

2. 24 hrs water boil

3. 1000 HRS, 70°C, 94% RH

TABLE 9

PROPERTIES OF BISMALIMIDE CROSS-LINKED POLYMERS

1. Insoluble in all solvents
2. Infusible, rigid, highly cross-linked
3. Brittle
4. Dense $\sim 1.35 - 1.40$ g/cc
5. High Tg $\sim 250-300^\circ\text{C}$
6. Low strain-to-failure 1.0-2.0%
7. Use temperature 150-200°C

The ease of processing, the high glass transition temperature, and the 150° to 200°C use temperature are desirable features of BMI resins. The processing characteristics are outlined in (Table 10).

TABLE 10

PROCESS CHARACTERISTICS OF BISMALEIMIDE RESINS

Epoxy-like processing

Autoclave cure

Low pressure

Require postcure

Autoclave cure:

80°C/1 hr (1.2-2.5°C/min.), 75-100 psi

177°C/4 hrs (1.2-2.5°C/min.), 75-100 psi

204°C/4hrs, 75-100 psi

Postcure:

220-260°C/4-24 hrs (freestanding)

Cool down:

1.5°C/min. to 50°C

However, the brittle nature and the low strain-to-failure are distinct disadvantages for BMI resins. For example the microcracking tendency of 90,0 cross-ply graphite/Bismaleimide composites and transverse strain-to-failure of unidirectional composites are compared in Table 11 (Ref. 39).

TABLE 11
Microcracking Behavior of Graphite
Bismaleimide (90/0) Cross-ply Composites

<u>Resin System</u>	<u>Graphite Fiber</u>	<u>Cracking Tendency</u>	<u>Transverse Tensile Stain-to-Failure %</u>
U.S. Polymeric V378A	HiTex 42	Severe	0.65
Hercules 4502	AS-4	Severe	0.59
Ferro CPI-2272	Celion 6000	Severe	0.60
Avco 151-2A	Celion	Moderate	0.74
AVCO 130-2A	AS-4	Severe	0.34
U.S. Polymeric XE 7078	HiTex 42	Moderate	0.67
Hexcel 1516	HiTex 42	Severe	-
AmCy X3100	HiTex 42	Severe	-
Narmco 5245C	IM6	None	0.72
5245C	HiTex 42	None	0.72

It can be seen that the BMI 5245C is the only one which resisted microcracking in 90,0 cross-ply composites. Fiber type and fiber surface properties undoubtedly influence the microcracking behavior of cross-ply composites. However the brittle nature of several BMI's is illustrated by comparing composite systems-containing the same fiber materials.

The trend in the development of bismaleimides is to increase the toughness characteristics (Table 12). This is being accomplished by modification of the basic BMI structure and/or by addition of reactive toughening agents. This is illustrated by Narmco 5245C which is an dicyanate, epoxy modified BMI. The fracture toughness of Narmco 5245C is more than that of a basic BMI, Kerimide 601 while Ciba-Geigy XU-292 (31) is approximately three times that of 5245C.

The increased toughness characteristics of both bismaleimides may be explained by formation of an interpenetrating polymer network within the cross-linked bismaleimide by the bisphenol monomer systems, thereby having a toughening influence within the bismaleimide resin system.

Bismaleimide compositions are also being used in adhesive formulations. An example of properties of a bismaleimide adhesive is shown in Table 13. Several companies are marketing bismaleimide adhesives, including American Cyanamid, Hysol, Hexcel and Technochemie.

This brief summary of state-of-the art poly (bismaleimides) for composite and adhesive applications is intended to focus on the types of polymers derived from bismaleimides, the properties generated both as resins and in composites and some of the advantages and disadvantages of such systems.

TABLE 12
Fracture Toughness of Some BMI Resins

System	K_{IC}		G_{IC}
	Psi in	Pa in	J/m ²
Kerimide 601 BMI	348	382	34 ¹
Narmco 5245C BMI (modified BMI)	516	567	74 ¹
Ciba Geigy XU-292	-	-	210 ²
Hexcel F178	-	-	29.4 ³

1. Assumes a modulus of 600,000 psi (ref 40)
2. (Ref. 31)
3. Hexcel data sheet

TABLE 13

HYSOL BISMALIMIDE MODIFIED EPOXY ADHESIVE

(EA 9655.1) Al-Al Joints

	<u>Tensile lap shear strength, psi</u>
RT	2600
RT - wet ¹	3600
232°C	2950
232°C - wet ¹	1700
232°C - aged 1000 hrs at 450°F	1750
260°C	1800
260°C	1400

1. 30 days, 120°F, 100% RH

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